

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Melo, M. R. de, Martins-Silva, P. de O., Andrade, A. L. de, & Moura, R. L. de. (2021). Barriers, adaptability, employability, and satisfaction: Career perceptions of Business students. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 25(6), e190124. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2021190124.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Melo, M. R. de, Martins-Silva, P. de O., Andrade, A. L. de, Moura, R. L. de., & Schröder, C. da S. (2021). Peer review report for: Barriers, adaptability, employability, and satisfaction: Career perceptions of Business students. RAC. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663062>

REVIEWERS:

 Christine da Silva Schröder (Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, EA, Brazil)

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Christine da Silva Schröder

Date review returned: June 11, 2019

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

Article presents an excellent theoretical-methodological contribution that is relatively innovative in a topic relevant to HRM in Brazil. My congratulations to the authors.

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of reviewers and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited. Only comments that violate the journal's ethical policies such as derogatory or defamatory comments will be edited (omitted) from the report. In these cases, it will be clearly stated that parts of the report were edited. Check [RAC's policies](#).

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?:

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: 1. Excellent

Quality: 1. Excellent

Originality: 1. Excellent

Overall: 1. Excellent

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Prezados Editores,

Agradecemos imensamente a oportunidade de realizar reformulações no manuscrito previamente submetido à Revista de Administração Contemporânea. Em nossa revisão, buscamos inserir as sugestões e recomendações feitas pelos revisores. Relacionamos abaixo todos os comentários que sugeriram modificações e as respectivas respostas.

Agradecemos mais uma vez a atenção dispensada para análise do nosso manuscrito.

Registro: ID RAC-2019-0124

Título do manuscrito: Barreiras, Adaptabilidade, Empregabilidade e Satisfação: Percepções de Carreira de Formandos em Administração

Data do envio da 1ª revisão: 07 de Janeiro de 2021

Avaliação Editor	Resposta (número de página):
1. O manuscrito recebeu dois pareceres razoavelmente a favor da publicação do trabalho. Solicito que os autores providenciem a revisão do <i>paper</i> conforme refere. E observem atentamente as orientações de formato que a RAC segue, por exemplo o resumo do manuscrito necessita ajuste.	Alterado. O manuscrito foi amplamente revisado conforme os pareceres emitidos pelos revisores e de acordo com as normas da revista. As respostas e as observações para cada solicitação estão indicadas na sequência.
Avaliação Revisor 1	Resposta (número de página):
Recomendação: Aceite	<i>Não aplicável</i>

[The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report].

Mais uma vez, agradecemos pelas considerações realizadas, e reafirmamos a nossa disponibilidade para conduzir quaisquer outras modificações e prestar outros esclarecimentos que julgarem necessários.

Atenciosamente,

Autores do manuscrito.

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